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Abstract

This study investigates the factors influencing the appropriation of ChatGPT by hotel employees in the Philippines using a descriptive-exploratory quantitative approach. Based on the Model of Technology Appropriation (MTA) and Task-Technology Fit (TTF) theory, the research examines how motivational, technological, and organizational factors affect employees' behaviors and perceptions regarding AI tool usage. A total of 179 hotel workers participated through voluntary sampling. Data were collected using survey instruments measuring Adoption Motivation (AM), TTF, Organizational Influence (OI), Adaptation Behavior, Integration Behavior (IB), and Appropriation Outcomes. PLS-R analysis revealed that TTF and IB significantly influenced employee perceptions of improved work efficiency and accuracy, while OI moderately contributed to positive outcomes. However, AM showed minimal long-term impact. These results underline the importance of continuous organizational support, clear guidelines, and practical task alignment for effective ChatGPT integration. This study provides valuable insights for hotel management on successful implementation of AI tools and highlights areas for future research, such as exploring cultural influences, organizational practices, and training effectiveness in technology adoption in similar setting.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing**; • **Human computer interaction (HCI)**; • **Empirical studies in HCI**;

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Keywords

AI in business, hotel employees, workplace technology adoption, AI integration

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1 INTRODUCTION

Hotels in the Philippines are beginning to explore artificial intelligence (AI) tools such as ChatGPT as part of their digital transformation initiatives [1, 2]. Employers are investing in these technologies to improve operational systems, provide quicker guest services, and reduce repetitive administrative work [3, 4]. These efforts show a growing interest in AI-driven solutions within the hospitality sector [5]. However, there is limited information on how hotel employees experience or respond to these tools in actual workplace conditions.

At the employee level, the extent of AI use remains unclear. While some hotel workers may have tested or used tools like ChatGPT [6, 7], others may not yet feel ready or confident to include them in their regular responsibilities [7]. Many employees do not receive formal training or guidance, and some are uncertain about whether the tool is suitable for their specific tasks [8, 9]. These conditions suggest that the use of AI depends not only on the technology itself but also on the support provided by the organization and the alignment between the tool and the nature of the employee's work [10, 11]. Earlier studies have found that hotel employees in the Philippines and Southeast Asia often lack formal training in AI, and their adoption behavior depends heavily on task relevance and

Table 1: Constructs, their Definitions, and Basis

Construct	Definition	Basis
AM	Reasons for initially trying ChatGPT	[15–17]
TTF	The degree to which ChatGPT supports task completion and job relevance.	[16, 18]
OI	The degree to which ChatGPT supports task completion and job relevance.	[19–21]
AB	How employees modify ChatGPT outputs to suit work tasks.	[16, 19, 22]
IB	Regular use of ChatGPT in daily job routines.	[18, 23, 24]
AO	Perceived improvements in efficiency, accuracy, and communication.	[16, 25]

organizational support [12, 13]. Employees who receive limited guidance and perceive a mismatch between AI functions and their roles are less likely to integrate these tools into their workflow [14].

This study examines how Filipino hotel employees engage with ChatGPT and what factors influence its use in their job roles. It applies the Model of Technology Appropriation (MTA) and the Task-Technology Fit (TTF) theory to explore motivation, organizational support, and task relevance. These frameworks were used in this study to help explain how employees start using, adjust to, and eventually integrate AI tools into their routines. By addressing the lack of evidence on employee-level AI experiences in Philippine hotels, the study offers practical knowledge that hotel managers and policy makers may use when planning future AI adoption in service settings. Based on the results of this study, the following objectives were addressed:

1. To explore the levels of TTF, Integration Behavior (IB), Organizational Influence (OI), Adaptation Behavior (AB), Adoption Motivation (AM), and perceived Appropriation Outcomes (AO) among hotel employees using ChatGPT;
2. To validate the measurement model for ChatGPT appropriation in hotel work by assessing the reliability and validity of all constructs;
3. To analyze the relative contributions of motivational (AM), technological (TTF), organizational (OI), and behavioral (AB, IB) factors to perceived AO; and
4. To identify which factors emerged as the most influential predictors of appropriation outcomes in the hospitality work context.

2 METHODS

This study employed a descriptive and exploratory quantitative research design to investigate the factors that influence ChatGPT appropriation among Filipino hotel employees. The research was guided by the MTA and TTF, which helped explain how motivational, technological, and organizational enablers relate to behavioral adaptation, integration, and perceived outcomes of AI use in hospitality work.

The participants were hotel employees currently working in various hotels across the Philippines. Respondents were eligible to participate if they had basic awareness of ChatGPT and had used it in their work tasks. A non-probability sampling method was used, and participation was voluntary and anonymous. Ethical standards were followed during data collection. Information about respondents' departments, hotel types, age, and work experience were reported in the Results section.

The survey measured six key constructs, each with three items rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). Table 1 summarizes the constructs used in the study. AM, TTF, and OI were used to represent motivational, technical, and contextual enablers. AB and IB measured how employees adjusted and incorporated the tool into their work routines. AO assessed perceived gains in efficiency, accuracy, and message quality.

Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS-R) was selected for the main analysis in this study. This method was appropriate due to its robustness in handling correlated variables and its suitability for moderate sample sizes [26], [27]. The model examined the effects of AM, TTF, OI, AB, IB, on AO. The model's performance was evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), mean squared error (MSE), and standardized regression coefficients. All analyses were performed using Python.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Respondents

A total of 179 hotel employees participated, comprising 52% males ($n = 93$) and 48% females ($n = 86$). The participants had an average age of 25.3 years, ranging from 17 to 58 years, and an average hospitality experience of 3.6 years, ranging from one to 38 years. Most respondents worked in food and beverage (52.5%, $n = 94$), followed by housekeeping (11.2%, $n = 20$), front office (7.8%, $n = 14$), and events and banquets (6.7%, $n = 12$). Smaller groups represented sales and marketing, culinary, reservations, finance, administration, and other supporting roles.

3.2 Reliability and Validity

All six constructs demonstrated strong reliability, exceeding the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70. Cronbach's alpha values were as follows: Adoption Motivation (AM, $\alpha = 0.865$), Task-Technology Fit (TTF, $\alpha = 0.891$), Organizational Influence (OI, $\alpha = 0.948$), Adaptation Behavior (AB, $\alpha = 0.958$), Integration Behavior (IB, $\alpha = 0.946$), and Appropriation Outcomes (AO, $\alpha = 0.948$).

On the other hand, convergent and discriminant validity were verified for all constructs. Each construct's average variance extracted (AVE) surpassed the recommended threshold of 0.50, while composite reliability (CR) values exceeded the acceptable threshold of 0.70. Item loadings were consistently high across all constructs. Discriminant validity was established using the Fornell-Larcker criterion, where each construct's AVE square root exceeded its correlation with other constructs. For instance, the AVE square root

Figure 1: PLS-R model of ChatGPT Appropriation

for AM was 0.887, higher than its correlations with TTF (0.687) and OI (0.672).

3.3 PLS-R Results

The PLS-R model explained 82% of the variance in appropriation outcomes (Figure 1, $R^2 = 0.82$). Task-Technology Fit exhibited the strongest predictive influence ($\beta = 0.305$), followed by Integration Behavior ($\beta = 0.236$), Organizational Influence ($\beta = 0.183$), Adaptation Behavior ($\beta = 0.175$), and Adoption Motivation ($\beta = 0.078$).

4 DISCUSSION

This study examined 179 hotel employees in the Philippines to determine the factors that influence the use of ChatGPT in their work. The PLS-R model explained 82% of the variance in appropriation outcomes. This result shows a strong relationship between the predictor variables and the outcomes. IB had the strongest influence ($\beta = 0.236$). This supports the MTA, which explains that technology use becomes meaningful when employees include it in their regular work routines [28]. Employees who use ChatGPT consistently are more likely to improve their efficiency and accuracy over time [29, 30]. TTF also had a significant effect ($\beta = 0.305$). ChatGPT use increases when it matches the nature of the employees' tasks, such as customer communication and administrative work [31].

OI had a moderate effect ($\beta = 0.183$). This result shows that support from the workplace, such as training and clear guidance, encourages productive use of ChatGPT [32, 33]. Local studies have also pointed out that support from colleagues and supervisors helps employees adopt new technologies [32]. AB showed a smaller but

meaningful effect ($\beta = 0.175$). Employees who edit and improve ChatGPT's responses tend to use the tool more effectively [34]. AM had the smallest effect ($\beta = 0.078$). This result means that curiosity or suggestions from others may encourage initial use, but these reasons are not enough to support long-term use [29, 35].

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study explored at how hotel employees in the Philippines use ChatGPT in their work. The analysis used standardized regression coefficients (β values) from the PLS-R model to compare the strength of each factor. The results shows that TTF had the strongest influence, showing the highest effect size among all predictors. Employees saw more benefits from ChatGPT when it matched their job tasks. Integration into daily work routines came next in importance. Support from the workplace and the ability to adjust ChatGPT outputs also helped employees make better use of the tool. However, the results also indicated that interest alone was not enough to sustain regular use.

These results suggest practical measures that hotel managers can implement to enhance the use of AI tools in the workplace specifically in hotel industry. Aligning AI applications with specific job tasks and integrating them into daily work processes can improve their relevance and sustainability. Providing clear operational guidelines, offering targeted training, and allowing employees to adjust AI outputs to fit their work requirements may lead to more meaningful use. Based on this study, there is a need for a structured implementation strategy because reliance solely on curiosity or informal peer suggestions among employees is unlikely to sustain AI adoption.

Future research can extend this work by examining how AI adoption influences measurable outcomes such as service quality and customer satisfaction. Longitudinal studies may capture changes in AI use over time, while mixed-method approaches that combine surveys with interviews can provide a deeper understanding of how AI functions within hotel operations.

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